

NOTES

13. FRED, BASOLO and RONALD C. JOHNSON, "Coordination Chemistry", W. A. Benjamin, Inc., New York, 1964, p. 115.
14. O. SAMUELSON, Studier Sorande Joubytaude fasta ammen, Stockholm, 1944.
15. G. E. BOYD, B. A. SOLDANO and O. D. BONNER, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1954, **58**, 456.
16. H. P. GREGOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 642.

A Selective and Sensitive Method for Detection of Nitro Compounds

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NITROCOMPOUNDS are of wide interest in industry where many of them find use as solvents and intermediates in the preparation of certain pharmaceuticals, insecticides, dyes, textile and explosive chemicals. This group of compounds, with few exceptions, has toxicological effects and causes methemoglobinemia in warm blooded animals and man⁷. For these reasons, the method for their detection and estimation in micro quantity carries special importance.

Some methods have been reported in the literature for the micro determination of nitro compounds¹⁻⁵ but very few methods are known for their detection in trace quantity⁶, none of which is applicable to both aliphatic and aromatic series of nitro compounds. The present method reported here is rapid and simple and is applicable for the detection of both the classes of nitro compounds.

The method is based on the fact that nitro compounds are reduced by zinc and ammonium chloride in neutral solution to the corresponding hydroxylamines which with acid chloride forms N-substituted hydroxamic acids. These hydroxamic acids give brilliant purple or blue-violet chloroform extractable complexes⁸ with V(V) in 3-8M hydrochloric acid medium. These coloured complexes can also be extracted in other water immiscible solvents such as benzene, ether, *o*-dichlorobenzene etc.

Experimental

Pure BDH and E. Merck nitro compounds were used. A stock solution of the nitro compounds was prepared by dissolving 5-100 mg of the compound

in alcohol in a 100 ml measuring flask. An aliquot of the stock solution was diluted to the desired concentration.

Procedure :

In a micro centrifuge tube mix 2 drops (approx. 0.1 ml) of sample solution (alcoholic) with 2-4 drops of water. To this add a pinch of ammonium chloride (2-3 mg) and zinc dust (3-4 mg). Shake well and heat for 2-4 minutes on a water bath at 70-80°, centrifuge and decant the supernatant liquid into a micro test tube. Wash the residue in the centrifuge tube with 0.5 ml ether and decant into the same micro test tube and shake. To this add one drop of benzoyl chloride and shake gently for some time. Add one drop of chloroform, 4 drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid and one drop of saturated solution of ammonium metavanadate. Shake the mixture vigorously for 2-3 min and allow the phases to separate. If nitro compound is present, the chloroform layer turns purple or blue violet. The colour development in the chloroform layer is more readily perceived when a white porcelain background is used.

This method was found suitable for the detection of a large number of nitro compounds. Identification limits of some of the nitro compounds were determined which are given in Table 1.

Phenols, salicylic acid and hydroxylamines interfere in the detection.

TABLE I

Compound	Colour of chloroform extract	Identification* limits, mg
Nitrobenzene	Violet	0.05
<i>o</i> -, <i>m</i> - and <i>p</i> -nitrotoluene	,,	0.05
<i>p</i> -chloronitrobenzene	,,	0.042
2 : 5 dichloronitrobenzene	,,	0.042
2-nitronaphthalene	Blue violet	0.045
Nitro methane	Purple	0.1
Nitro ethane	,,	0.1

* These quantities were present in 0.1 ml of sample solution.

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References

1. OTKRYTIYA, IZOBRET, PROM. OBRAZTSY, TOVARNYE ZNAKI, 1971, **48**, 167.
2. R. D. TIWARI and U. C. YANDE, *J. Microchem.*, 1972, **17**, 476.

3. J. BARTOS, *Analysis*, 1973, 2, 411.
4. R. D. TIWARI, U. C. PANDE, M. GOPAL and G. SHRIVASTAVA, *Z. analyt. Chem.*, 1976, 278, 367.
5. J. P. RAWAT and J. P. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem*, 1978, 16A, 551.
6. FEIGL, "Spot Tests in Organic Analysis", Elsevier, New York, 1975, p, 295.
7. O. BODANSKY, *Pharmacol. Revs.*, 1951, 3, 144.
8. U. PRIVADARSHINI and S. G. TANDON, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1960, 931.

Stage II Annealing of Chemical Radiation Damage in Strontium Nitrate

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THE isothermal annealing of chemical radiation damage in various ionic nitrates has been investigated and it has been observed that the recovery takes place as a continuous process¹⁻⁵. In some preliminary investigations on isochronal annealing and annealing in linear tempering of chemical radiation damage in γ -irradiated strontium nitrate in this laboratory it has been observed that the recombination takes place in two stages, one between 180-260° and the other above 260°. The details of the

kinetics of the recovery process in the temperature range 180-260° have already been reported⁶. This communication reports the kinetics of the thermal annealing process taking place in the second stage (270-300°).

Experimental

The same sample of irradiated strontium nitrate employed in the previous investigations⁶ was used. Isothermal runs were made in the temperature range 270-300° as before. The analytical procedure followed was also the same as that reported earlier⁶.

Results and Discussion

Data on the kinetics of annealing are presented in Fig. 1. The φ -t characteristic is the same as that obtained in the lower temperature range. The magnitude of annealing in the higher temperature range is greater as expected.

The annealing data obtained have been analysed on the basis of models developed by Fletcher and Brown^{6,7} and by Waite^{8,9} for interstitial vacancy recombination and also on the basis of conventional chemical kinetics¹⁰. The application of Fletcher-Brown treatment^{6,7} shows that the annealing data fit the following combination of a first order and second order process

$$\varphi = 0.14[1 - \exp(-t'/1.031)] + 0.86[1/1 + 297.6/t']$$

where φ is the fraction annealed and t' the equivalent time of annealing⁶ at 280°. The activation

Fig. 1. Annealing of γ -irradiation damage in strontium nitrate.

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